

D. 6.3 – Report on the influential communities of actors and stakeholders in energy transition for SDGs

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Report on the influential communities of actors and stakeholders in energy transition for SDGs

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Background

“No country is on track to meeting the goal of gender equality – without which none of the others will be met, and in fact, the gap in several [of them] is growing.” (Antonio Guterres, 2020)

Gender indicators are only beginning to be developed and measured for the energy sector, and initial data sets for tracking progress are patchy.¹

SDGs and gender

Of the 17 goals of the UN Agenda 2030, eight have no gender-related targets or indicators/

Figure 1. SDG targets organised by the presence of gender-related targets. Eight goals are completely silent on gender

UN Women developed 120 gender-related indicators but the ones that are achievable because comparable statistical data are being collected cover only six SDGs

¹ https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/2022-UN_SDG7%20Brief-060122.pdf

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A more complete picture is needed of what improved "access" means from a gender perspective. To get a better picture of better access to energy, we need to include analysis of gender equality issues at household-, community-, and productive-use levels.

Applying a gender lens to each and every goal of the Agenda 2030 can help reveal previously overlooked interconnections between different targets with shared gender equality benefits by identifying and connecting biological, social, cultural, and situational gender dimensions of sustainability and development, creating a more holistic and multi-level understanding of synergies between different targets.

Whilst many attempts have been made since 2015 to interconnect different goals to identify strategically beneficial implementation efforts, in almost all cases, the significance of SDG5 has been ignored.²

The absence of: 1) of clear gender targets in the descriptions of the majority of goals; and/or of 2) gender experts among professionals analysing potential interconnections between the goals (see Figure 4 below); and/or of 3) research studies on SDGs with a gender dimension, see Figure 5 below, has contributed to the disappointing progress of achieving gender equality ambitions in Agenda 2030.³ There is also pervading absence of attention to gender equality benefits in energy transition policy frameworks, which may be directed at "people", "society", "citizens", "households", but without considerations if the outcomes will benefit women and men equally.

²https://www.portiaweb.org.uk/assets/docs/UNW_Gender_Analysis_Toolkit_for_Prioritising_SDG_Goals_and_Targets.pdf

³https://portiaweb.org.uk/assets/docs/Applying_gender_lens_to_the_interlinkages_and_synergies_betweenSDGs.pdf

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SDG	Number of respondents (groups 1-4)	Number of respondents (group 5: IISD mailing list)	Number of respondents (group 5), filtered	Number of respondents (together)	Number of respondents (together), filtered
SDG 1	0	3	2	3	2
SDG 2	0	1	1	1	1
SDG 3	2	2	1	4	3
SDG 4	1	5	1	6	2
SDG 5	0	0	0	0	0
SDG 6	1	2	2	3	3
SDG 7	3	4	3	7	6
SDG 8	0	4	0	4	2
SDG 9	1	0	0	1	1
SDG 10	1	0	0	1	1
SDG 11	3	4	4	7	7
SDG 12	0	3	3	3	3
SDG 13	0	3	3	3	3
SDG 14	1	0	0	1	1
SDG 15	3	4	2	7	5
SDG 16	1	4	2	5	3
SDG 17	2	4	4	6	6

Figure 4. Example of excluding gender expertise from expert considerations of interlinkages between different SDGs

Figure 5. Analysis of gender content of research studies on different SDGs: only 1% of research on SDG7 include considerations of gender issues.⁴

Figure 5 shows that for SDG7 (energy) only 1% of research studies have included consideration of gender dimensions. This demonstrates an urgent need to produce

⁴ Herbert, Rachel and Falk-Krzyszynski, Holly J. and Plume, Andrew, Sustainability Through a Gender Lenses: The Extent to Which Research on UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Includes Sex and Gender Consideration (September 8, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3689205>

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evidence and knowledge that explains what happens at the nexus of gender equality and energy transition. We know that traditional energy systems are deeply gendered in terms of underrepresentation of women in the workforce and in decision-making roles but also that they harbour multiple gender and social differences in how women and men use energy.

Developing indicators interlinking SDG7 and SDG5

Making women visible in sustainable energy and highlighting the importance of expanding the gender lens on energy data collection can focus attention on key gender gaps in the energy sector and on how to better achieve gender equality in the energy sector.⁵ Gender indicators are only beginning to be developed and measured for the energy sector, and initial data sets for tracking progress are patchy. The table below exemplifies first propositions for SDG7-related gender indicators, and lists key partners involved in and influencing the exercise.⁶

A Technical Working Group on Gender and Energy Interlinkages, comprising key partners in the table above, has been proposed. The aim of the Group could be to undertake to prioritize further indicators and areas for coordination on data collection on gender and energy. Another task for the Group would be also identifying next steps in methodology development and refinement of indicators, political buy-in for the indicators, and communication to governments and other stakeholders on the urgency of data collection on gender and energy, as well as progress on an annual basis.⁷

⁵ https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/2022-UN_SDG7%20Brief-060122.pdf

⁶ https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/2022-UN_SDG7%20Brief-060122.pdf

⁷ https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-06/2022-UN_SDG7%20Brief-060122.pdf

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Table 1: Proposed and Possible Further Indicators for SDG 7/SDG 5 Interlinkages

Definition	Key partners	Aligns with
2.1 Proposed indicators with available data		
2.1.1 Proportion of population with access to electricity, disaggregated by female-headed and male-headed households.	World Bank, MTF, OPHI	SDG 7.1.1
2.1.2 Proportion of population with primary reliance on clean fuels and technology, disaggregated by female-headed and male-headed households.	WHO, MTF, OPHI	SDG 7.1.2
2.1.3 Whether or not national, regional, and international energy policies and frameworks are in place that promote, enforce, and monitor equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex.	RISE/World Bank, UN Women	SDG 5.1.1 SDG 5.C.1
2.2 Other indicators with some available data		
For Energy Poverty/Access gender gap:		
A financial target such as "Annual tracked commitments to clean cooking" or the "cost of inaction" on cooking energy	Clean Cooking Alliance	SDG 7.1.2
Proportion of time spent on fuel collection and cooking by men and women	MTF, RISE	SDG 5.4
Proportion of households with lighting in kitchen/access to electrical appliances and end-uses that reduce unpaid care work	MTF, CLASP	SDG 7.1.1 SDG 5.4
Proportion of educational facilities with adequate electricity/clean cooking, by boys'/girls' schools	UNESCO, MTF	SDG 4
Mortality rate attributed to household and ambient air pollution, age-standardized, female (per 100,000 female population) (Indicator SDG 3.9.1)	WHO	SDG 3.9.1
For Employment and Leadership gender gap:		
Proportion (%) of women employed in the energy value chain for technical and administrative jobs related to the energy/renewable energy sector	IFC, ILO, IRENA, ESMAP, RISE/World Bank, IEA, UN Women	SDG 7.2 SDG 8
Proportion of women in managerial positions and proportion of women in senior and middle management positions in the energy sector	ILO, IRENA, ESMAP, RISE, OECD/IEA, UN Women	SDG 5.5.2
Proportion of women in senior political positions in relevant ministries, national energy agencies and entities	IRENA, RISE, IEA, UN Women, Clean Energy Ministerial	SDG 5.5.2
For Entrepreneurship gender gap:		
Proportion of male and female-owned businesses with electricity connections	UNIDO, UN Women	SDG 8
Proportion of women and men energy owners/managers of established energy businesses	Global Economic Monitor/World Bank, IFC, UNIDO, UN Women	SDG 8
2.3.3 Proportion of finance available for women-led and men-led energy businesses	IFC, UNIDO, UN Women	SDG 8
2.4 For Enabling Environment gender gap:		
2.4.2 Tracking systems and budget allocations for gender equality in the energy sector	RISE/World Bank, UN Women, OECD/DAC	SDG 5.C.1

Key to new acronyms: Collaborative Labeling and Appliance Standards Program (CLASP); The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO); International Finance Corporation (IFC); International Labour Organization (ILO); International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA); International Energy Agency (IEA); Development Assistance Committee (DAC).

Investigating gendered power relations in energy transition: the Horizon Europe gEneSys project

The topic of gendered power relations in energy transition is of direct concern for the EU Horizon Europe gEneSys project⁸, which is examining the why's and how's of energy transition efforts through the gender lens. gEneSys examines energy transition as an ecosystem of potentially collaborating or competing sub-systems of actors, stakeholders, each with some mission on what energy transition outcomes to prioritise.

⁸ www.genesys-project.eu

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These priorities may be in conflict with the goals promoted in the other parts of the ecosystem. The core subsystems examined by gEneSys include the governance, society, environment, technology, policy, and economy.

Figure 6. The gEneSys model of energy transition as an ecosystem

The outputs from gEneSys are available on Zenodo.⁹

Making women visible as energy transition actors

Applying the gender lens to energy transition efforts in the EU, should also include assessment of opportunities to make these efforts more effective by deploying the EU's commitment to gender equality as a core policy principle of the Union, and also the EU's commitment to mainstream gender into all parts of the EU budget, as recommended in the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027.¹⁰

At present, a system of 'coefficients' is used to grade EU climate interventions¹¹, but the gradings do not allow for the possibility that some EU spending causes harm; there is evidence that support for agriculture can increase carbon emissions, yet is not picked up by the methodology. A similar approach has recently been adopted for assessing the gender focus of EU spending, with '2', '1', '0*' and '0' gradings, ranging from whether the measure is principally gender related to having no gender content. In response to criticism from the ECA about gender mainstreaming, the Commission has strengthened its approach. Nevertheless only 11% of EU spending in 2023 was shown to be on gender measures, of which 2 percentage points were deemed to be the principal aim of the intervention and 9 points important, but secondary. However,

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/genesys/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

¹⁰ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/performance-and-reporting/horizontal-priorities/gender-equality-mainstreaming_en

¹¹ At present, any spending is supposed to be assessed using coefficients of 0% (no effect), 40% (a non-marginal positive effect) or 100% (a substantial contribution to climate change mitigation). A possible refinement to overcome the large gap between 40% and 100% would be to adopt a five point scale: 0%, 25%, 50% 75% and 100%.

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it is already clear that the targets for biodiversity (a new goal for the current MFF) will be missed, and there is little evidence of the EU budget affecting the SDGs.

The current EU policy is clear: transitions to low-carbon energy systems are essential to meeting the EU's and global commitments to climate change mitigation. Yet, research show that “greening” energy systems may not make them any fairer, inclusive or just than the traditional energy systems are.¹² Renewable energy projects alone cannot achieve gender and social equity, because energy interventions do not automatically tackle the structural dynamics of gender inequality embedded within socio-cultural, socio-economic, policy, and governance contexts.

The recent JRC report¹³, produced in collaboration with the Dutch expert centre on diversity in the energy transition, 75inQ, emphasises the importance of inclusive policies in guaranteeing women's active engagement and representation in the energy industry, not just as customers but also as decision-makers and innovators. The report highlights the significance of breaking down traditional policy silos, providing a road map for a more integrated and comprehensive approach to addressing the complex causes of energy poverty. The findings of the study stress the need of strong data collection and monitoring methods for tracking the success of gender-inclusive energy transition activities, enabling for informed and targeted interventions at both the national and European levels.

Future outlook on gender equality commitments in Europe

In March 2024, the Council of Europe adopted new Gender Equality Strategy for 2024-2029¹⁴, organised around the following principles

- Preventing and combating gender stereotypes and sexism
- Preventing and combating violence against women and girls and domestic violence
- Ensuring equal access to justice for women and girls
- Achieving balanced participation of women and men in political, public, social and economic life
- Ensuring women's empowerment and gender equality in relation to global and geopolitical challenges
- Achieving gender mainstreaming and including an intersectional approach in all policies and measures
- The early political guidelines for the next European Commission 2024-2029, presented by Ursula von der Leyen in July 2024¹⁵ includes strong commitment to gender equality:

¹² <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629620303492>

¹³ How to cite this report: Murauskaite-Bull I., Feenstra M., Creusen A., Koukoufikis G., Della Valle N., Shortall R., Stojilovska A., Gender and energy: the effects of the energy transition on women, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2024, doi:10.2760/860118, JRC132744

¹⁴ [https://search.coe.int/cm/#{%22CoEIdentifier%22:\[%220900001680ae569b%22\],%22sort%22:\[%22CoEValidationDate%20Descending%22\]}](https://search.coe.int/cm/#{%22CoEIdentifier%22:[%220900001680ae569b%22],%22sort%22:[%22CoEValidationDate%20Descending%22]})

¹⁵ https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/e6cd4328-673c-4e7a-8683-f63ffb2cf648_en?filename=Political%20Guidelines%202024-2029_EN.pdf

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To strengthen our commitment, we will propose a new Gender Equality Strategy for post-2025. It will set out our plan to strengthen women's rights across the board, from the fight against gender-based violence to empowering women in politics and the labour market, across the EU, as well as across the EU institutions.

On a negative side, however, while both gender and energy transition are set to feature in the work of the new European Commission over the coming years, pursuing the nexus between the two policy goals are not connected. The priority issues for energy are linked to energy security, economic competitiveness, markets, infrastructures and technologies, e.g.,

We will scale-up and prioritise investment in clean energy infrastructure and technologies. This will include renewables and low-carbon technologies, grid infrastructure, storage capacity and transport infrastructure for captured CO₂. We will also invest in energy efficiency measures, the digitalisation of our energy system and the deployment of a hydrogen network.

Influential stakeholder organisations in the energy transition ecosystem

Networks of women and for women in energy

Below is a non-exhaustive list of women's networks in energy

- Aemener (Spanish Association of Women for Energy)
- Global Women's Network for the Energy Transition (GWNET)
- Women's Environment & Development Organization (WEDO)
- Women Engage for Commo Future
- Women in Green Hydrogen
- Light on Women Initiative of the European University Institute
- Woman of the Arctic

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Women Energy Network
Women Engage for Common Future
Women in Cleantech & Sustainability
Women in Energy - Iceland
Women in Energy Chile
Women in Energy EU
Women in Fusion
Women in Green Hydrogen
Women in Mining
Women in Mining Spain
Women in Nuclear Global
Women in Renewable Energy (WiRE)
Women for Renewable Energy Sources
Women in Solar Energy
Women in Wind
Women of New Energies
Women of Offshore Wind
Women of Renewable Industries and Sustainable Energy
Women's Energy Network Alliance

The EU strategy on SDGs

The European Union has made formal commitments to 1) advancing gender equality, e.g., through the EU's Gender Action Plan III¹⁶; 2) becoming a climate-neutral and climate resilient continent by 2050 as enshrined in Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 on the European Climate Law¹⁷, and 3) delivery on the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030.

The EU's SDG agenda is aligned with the EU's political mission¹⁸. Figure 7, below, shows how actions on the different SDGs are connected to the EU's core political goals.

¹⁶ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/gender-action-plan-iii-towards-gender-equal-world_en

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ('European Climate Law'), OJ L 243, 9.7.2021, p. 1.

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0739>

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Figure 7. Figure showing how the Commission's political programme addresses the SDGs¹⁹

Relevant but not integrated into the EU's response to Agenda 2030 goals is the EU's Gender Action Plan III²⁰, the duration of which has been extended until 2027. GA Plan III seeks to position gender equality and women's empowerment as central priorities across all EU internal and external policies and actions. One significant example of EU's SDG-related external action is the Global Gateway Strategy, *Women for Stronger Communities and Growth*²¹, the aim of which is to empower women and communities across Africa, Asia, Latin America, Caribbean and Pacific to build and reinforce resilience towards climate change, food insecurity, as well as offering new opportunities for jobs and growth.

These bindings are part of the EU's Communications on the European Green Deal²² and in the vision for a Strong Social Europe for Just Transition²³, and the Commission's ambitions to upgrade Europe's social market economy to achieve a just transition to sustainability.

The actors and stakeholders helping fulfil the EU's SDGs implementation ambitions are partner countries, Member States and public authorities at different levels, civil society and private sector, as well as participants in high-level international fora, including the United Nations High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development.

¹⁹ In the figure, the SDGs are represented under a specific Commission political priority to which they are strongly associated, while noting that most SDGs contribute to varying degrees to several priorities.

²⁰ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/gender-action-plan-iii-towards-gender-equal-world_en

²¹ <https://www.eib.org/en/press/all/2025-259-global-gateway-strategy-delivers-and-mobilises-partners-for-women-s-economic-empowerment-and-strong-communities-around-the-world>

²² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>.

²³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0014>.

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The European Green Deal

The European Green Deal²⁴ aims to transform the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, ensuring:

- no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050
- economic growth decoupled from resource use
- no person and no place left behind

Whilst the Green Deal calls for just and fair outcomes, it does not explicitly consider how gender equality fits into this vision.

The Green Deal's *Fit for 55* rules set out laws aiming to **reduce EU greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030** and put the EU on the path to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, with the aims to:

- ensure a just and socially fair transition
- maintain and strengthen innovation and competitiveness of EU industry while ensuring a level playing field vis-à-vis third country economic operators
- underpin the EU's position as leader in the global fight against climate change

The study commissioned by the European Parliament analysed (i) whether a gender dimension has been incorporated in the initiatives proposed under the Fit for 55 package and (ii) whether a gender-sensitive approach was used in policy formulation.²⁵ The study concluded that there is limited recognition of gender and other social categories in terms of the potential impacts of the initiatives that make up the Fit for 55 package, as well as the roles that different groups of citizens can play in making the energy transition work, and very little attempt to adopt a gender-sensitive and socially inclusive approach.

The EU's 'whole government' approach to SDGs

Figure 8. The European Commission's comprehensive or "whole of government" approach²⁶

²⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

²⁵ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/736899/IPOL_STU\(2022\)736899_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2022/736899/IPOL_STU(2022)736899_EN.pdf)

²⁶ https://sdgtoolkit.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/EU-staff_working_document-delivering_on_uns_sustainable_development_goals_en.pdf

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- Designing and effectively applying deeply transformative policies
- The European Semester of economic governance: coordination of economic policies
- The Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) and the recovery instrument 'Next Generation EU'
- Mainstreaming the SDGs in policymaking using better regulation tools
- Ensuring policy coherence for sustainable development
- EU engagement in the world
- Monitoring and reporting
- Engagement of civil society, private sector and other stakeholders.

Gender and Transformative Policies

The energy transition in Europe offers an opportunity to tackle and eliminate energy-related gender inequalities. Building new relationships in terms of consumption, production, supply, and governance can eliminate the inequalities so evident in the old – fossil fuel-based – energy system. The energy transition can be conceptualised as a tool to amplify gender equality. Doing so recognises and reaffirms the deeply political nature of energy systems (change).²⁷

Gender and the European Semester of economic governance

European Parliament resolution of 12 March 2025 on the European Semester for economic policy coordination: employment and social priorities for 2025 (2024/2084(INI)) included a reference to gender equality in relation to SDGs that welcomed the inclusion of analysis on the positive contribution of the SDGs and the European equality strategies in the JER 2025 and called on the Commission to

ensure that the JER 2026 includes both a section analysing the progress towards the SDGs related to employment and social policy, and another on progress towards eliminating social and labour discrimination in line with the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, the EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020-2025, the EU Roma strategic framework for equality, inclusion and participation 2020-2030, the LGBTIQ Equality Strategy 2020- 2025, and the Strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities 2021-2030

Gender and the Multiannual Financial Framework

The European Commission has committed to implementing gender mainstreaming, and the European Parliament and the Council have emphasised the need for the EU to deliver on its high-level gender-mainstreaming commitments. The three institutions, when negotiating both the 2014-2020 and the 2021-2027 multiannual financial frameworks (MFFs), agreed on the importance of considering gender equality in EU budgeting.²⁸

²⁷ <https://gef.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/political-brief-gender-energy.pdf>

²⁸ <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eca/special-reports/gender-10-2021/en/>

Gender and SDGs policy making

A UN DESA used text mining approach to map EU policies to Agenda 2030. This exercise screened 1700 documents from 2016 until 2020. The results revealed that all 17 goals are addressed by EU actions, with special emphasis on SDG 8, 16 and 3. At target level, the analysis identified strong link between the EU Recovery Plan and all SDGs, with 94 targets addressed in the documents. Most of the detected keywords relate to SDG 3 (with prevalence of target 3.d) and SDG 8, but the analysis identified targets pertaining to all other SDGs, among which higher numbers were in SDG13, SDG4, SDG16 and SDG9.

The tool for policy mapping is available on the JRC KnowSDGs platform <https://knowsdgs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>. The JRC tool currently identifies 9718 EU policy documents related to SDGs and categorises these according to which SDG's are part of the context of each document. Figure 9 below shows how very little connection there is between SDG7 and SDG5 in the EU policy documents for the years 2019-2024 in comparison to other goals. The same pattern occurs when comparing policy documents for 2015-2019.

Figure 9. Connections between SDG7 and other SDGs identified in the EU policy documents for 2019-2024 (source JRC KnowSDGs platform)

Gender and policy coherence

Figure 10 below shows policy coherence between SDG5 and other SDGs sourced on the JRC KnowSDGs platform. The tool counts the number of policy documents (in the total of around 9700 in the period 2019-2024) that mention both SDG5 and another SDG. It is interesting to note the low coherence between SDG5 and SDG13 (climate action) and the very high coherence between SDG5 and SDG16 (Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions).

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Figure 10. Connections between SDG5 and other SDGs identified in the EU policy documents for 2019-2024 (source JRC KnowSDGs platform)

As primary household caretakers in most societies, women are disproportionately affected by the lack of access to sustainable forms of energy. Women and men have distinct energy needs and consumption patterns as they typically occupy different social roles in most countries where men are often responsible for providing household income while women are responsible for domestic duties and sometimes for securing an additional income in parallel. In rural areas in developing countries, women and girls carry out the bulk of household work. Access to energy significantly affects their health and well-being, and in turn, those of their families and communities. In developing countries, girls and women spend long hours gathering biomass (mainly wood), which takes up valuable time and restricts their access to education and paid work.

As primary energy managers in households, women in both developed and developing countries can play a key role in promoting sustainable energy consumption patterns and accelerating the shift to renewable energy. Evidence suggests that women are more responsible users of energy than men. Recent studies in Europe have shown that single men directly or indirectly use up to 22% more energy than single women.

Gender and EU Engagement in the world

The policy framework for the EU's development cooperation was laid out in the European Consensus on Development, which sets the political vision underlying the financial proposals of the Multi-Annual Financial Framework (2021-2027). The core objective remains the eradication of poverty and the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations' (UN) 2030 Agenda, tackling challenges related to human development, inclusive and sustainable growth, climate change, environmental degradation, migration and mobility, as well as

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promote governance, democracy and human rights. The objectives of the Multi-Annual Indicative Programme for Sub-Saharan Africa²⁹ on cooperation with Africa include promoting gender equality, inclusion and a human rights-based approach as well as investing in women and youth. It also includes green transition: climate mitigation and resilience, sustainable energy, sustainable agri-food systems, biodiversity and environment, and water and oceans.

Gender and SDG monitoring and reporting

The EU SDG indicator set comprises around 100 indicators and is structured along the 17 SDGs.³⁰ For each SDG, it focuses on aspects that are relevant from an EU perspective. The annual monitoring report provides a statistical presentation of trends relating to the SDGs in the EU over the past five years ('short-term') and, when sufficient data are available, over the past 15 years ('long-term'). The indicator trends are described on the basis of a set of specific quantitative rules. The 2023 edition³¹ reports on positive advancement for SDG5 but progress on SDG7 has been only "slight".

Gender and engagement of civil society, private sector and other stakeholders

Advancing just transitions through the lens of gender is vital for addressing systemic inequalities and fostering fairer outcomes in the economic, technological, environmental, and social changes that accompany the energy transition. The European Parliament has called for a platform or a forum on the SDGs to be established to foster a structured engagement with civil society, youth organisations, businesses, trade unions and scientists in SDG related policy development and monitoring.³²

The citizens' active participation in energy projects will transform and, to some extent, is already transforming the traditional energy system, it is only recently that its configurations have been formally included within European regulations.³³ For example, the "Clean Energy for All Europeans" is a package of eight legislative proposals presented by the European Union in 2016. The European Directive 2001/2018 (RED II)³⁴ introduces the concept and a formal definition of the "Renewable Energy Community" (REC) for the first time.

²⁹ https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/document/download/44e52b4e-a332-4c31-bb41-c119ba73f295_en

³⁰ https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/38a1e5be-e584-49df-82a9-0ebd9133e9d1_en?filename=SDG-Report-WEB.pdf

³¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/15234730/16817772/KS-04-23-184-EN-N.pdf/845a1782-998d-a767-b097-f22ebe93d422?version=2.0&t=1688373085450>

³² https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/38a1e5be-e584-49df-82a9-0ebd9133e9d1_en?filename=SDG-Report-WEB.pdf

³³ <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/16/10/4122>

³⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/2001/oj/eng>

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Figure 11. Using SDG17 to promote global actions for development. SDG5 is included across all five focus areas. SDG7 is covered in Climate and Energy but not in Sustainable Transport.

In 2021, the EU launched the Global Gateway initiative to strengthen the means of implementation and revitalise the global partnership (SDG 17), with a view to pursuing the 2030 Agenda and its SDGs. Global Gateway helps promote greater public and private investments in sustainable connectivity, notably through transport, energy and digitalisation infrastructure, and related people to people connections (in health and education).

Another initiative under the Development Cooperation Instrument, is the Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI)³⁵ is the EU's flagship initiative to increase access to clean energy in developing countries, which contributes to SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy).

The EU's collaborative approach to engagement of actors and stakeholders in energy transition

The EU delivers on energy transition goals in a collaborative approach through the initiatives listed below. So far, these initiatives have been gender blind in relation to recognising the benefits of advancing gender equality benefits in and through energy transition efforts.

> The EU [Sustainable Energy Week](#) is the biggest event in the EU on renewables and energy efficiency, bringing together policymakers, industries and citizens. Gender equality has not received much attention in the programme for the last three years, even when the topics included in the discussions have a clear gender dimension, e.g., What can European and national policymakers, educational institutions and industry do to ignite the skill revolution? Which new skills are needed in the light of the transformation of the European energy market and system? How to engage the young

³⁵ <https://edfimc.eu/what-we-do/electrifi/>

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in a clean energy career? How can the EU ensure affordable housing that aligns with the green transition goals? What financing solutions can make energy efficient and renewables-based housing accessible to low- and middle-income groups?

> The EU [Energy Days](#) gather key clean energy players to promote and strengthen cooperation on sustainable, secure and smart energy solutions. These events, especially when aligned with COP events could be an opportunity to showcase the experience of women in promoting clean energy and advancing research and innovation on sustainable energy systems.

> The [European Sustainable Energy Awards](#) aim to highlight individuals, including women through the Women in Energy Award, and initiatives that are contributing to Europe's clean and digital energy transition. Past programmes focused on technology-centred policies and have not included discussions on gender equality. The Women in Energy Award recognises women who lead outstanding activities that, if replicated, help to advance the clean energy transition in Europe. Particular attention is placed on efforts to drive the gender mainstreaming agenda and support equality and equal opportunities in the energy sector.

> The [Energy Infrastructure Forum](#) was set up in 2015 as part of the energy union strategy, which aims to remove technical and regulatory barriers to energy flowing freely across the EU, to discuss major issues relating to infrastructure and EU energy policy. The Forum serves as a platform for policy makers and stakeholders to exchange views, and the aims to ensure that new EU legislation related to energy infrastructure is goal-oriented, operational and comprehensive.

> The [Clean Energy Industrial Forum](#) develops recommendations on how to strengthen the industrial basis and the EU value chain for renewable energy technologies. The Forum has already put in place some examples of initiatives aiming to strengthen the skill basis of European workers, with a view to also target women. The Forum targets attracting more women to clean energy related jobs and fostering their representation and retaining them in technical and in STEM fields but increase their employment rate.³⁶ The European Master in Renewable Energy (EMRE) and the European Master in Sustainable Energy Management (SESyM) coordinated by EUREC are good examples of postgraduate programmes taught across 9 European countries that offers specialisation on a renewable energy technology of choice. EIT InnoEnergy provides an innovative solution in addressing STEM skills identified in clean energy and the green transition, with Master degree programmes across top universities Europe, which include collaboration with the industry as well as entrepreneurial aspects.

> The [Citizens' Energy Forum](#) meets on an annual basis and aims to explore the consumer perspective and role in a competitive, smart, energy-efficient and fair energy retail market. The forum serves to structure the debate and channel consumers', regulators' and industry's view on the energy market and its future, directly feeding into the work of the European Commission in the energy and consumer policy areas. Citizen participation schemes in RES-E are characterized by both decentralization and the congruence of investment and possession. Ideally, local

³⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2022-06/ceif_joint_statement_on_skills.pdf

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citizens are the driving force in each step of the plants' realization: planning, mobilization of resources and its operative implementation. The Forum brings together a wide range of local stakeholders representing NGOs, cities, energy communities, energy agencies, consumer associations, businesses and citizens to exchange on challenges and solutions to effectively empower citizens on the ground to ensure a fair and inclusive energy transition.

> In line with the [European industrial strategy](#), launched in March 2020, aiming at supporting the twin transition to a green and digital economy, the EU is developing industrial alliances to accelerate the development of key projects that support the manufacturing of low-carbon energy technologies (batteries, hydrogen, etc.) and which will maintain the EU's leadership in innovative and green technologies. The Forum aims to support the Commission in its systematic analysis of the different industrial ecosystems and in assessing the different risks and needs of industry as it embarks on the twin digital and green transitions, and the strengthening of its resilience, including working to increase the pool of EU talent, helping people acquire new technology-based skills. The strategy includes an SME strategy that aims to reduce red tape and help Europe's SMEs to do business across the single market and beyond, access financing, and help lead the way on the digital and green transitions.

Emerging challenges

Monitoring progress on SDGs, gender mainstreaming, and energy transition in the EU through internal mechanisms, and also externally, is crucial. There are indicators for keeping an eye on climate and biodiversity, and change can be easier tracked than progress on gender or the SDGs.

The tool for tracking action on climate is the Climate Adjustment Mechanism which is described in a Commission document on the climate mainstreaming architecture. Methodologies for gender and SDG mainstreaming are missing measurable expected results or impacts, as there are no specific targets associated with these mainstreaming goals. The decision on whether the EU should intensify mainstreaming efforts on SDG objectives in the post Agenda 2030 era will be political and subject to the emerging geopolitical challenges.³⁷

In June 2025, the EU launched the Energy Union Task Force to reinforce and enhance coordination and governance across the energy union.³⁸ The core concern is energy security in the world of dramatic upheavals in energy supply caused by the war in Ukraine. The Energy Union Task Force is a strategic initiative under the Action Plan for Affordable Energy. The aim is to work towards further integrating the EU energy systems and strengthen the governance of the electricity system. Key priorities include optimising the use of energy infrastructure, accelerating interconnectivity, improving grid and energy system planning coordination among Member States, providing support in the monitoring of national action to implement the Action Plan, and discussing areas of mutual interests related to EU energy legislation implementation. The Task Force will receive support from relevant EU institutions and agencies, such as

³⁷ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/766172/IPOL_BRI\(2024\)766172_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/766172/IPOL_BRI(2024)766172_EN.pdf)

³⁸ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/strategy/energy-union_en

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the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the Agency for the Cooperation of Energy Regulators (ACER), as well as from technical experts, when appropriate.

Conclusions

The focus of the gEneSys project is to understand gendered power relations in energy transition efforts, pathways, and outcomes. The aim of this report is to highlight the key communities of actors and stakeholders who shape the EU policies and implementation efforts in support of energy transition and SDGs at the highest level. It is clear, that policy coherence between SDG5 and SDG7 is much weaker than in the policies connecting other goals. gEneSys analysis of research at the nexus of energy and gender has shown disconnection between evidence- and knowledge-making and translating this work into policy recommendations. Science is expected to engage with policy makers by providing a useful causal analysis of specific problems, but policymakers need evidence that helps inform how to achieve specific outcomes and in the context of energy transition, the indicators of "fair" and "just" outcomes, and how gender equality fits into this, are not clear at present.

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